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COMMITTEE OF UNION AND PROGRESS: OFFICIAL INTERPRETATION OF POLITICAL IDEOLOGY OF OTTOMANISM (1908-1916)

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Abstract

In 1908, after of a military coup, the party of Committee of Unity and Progress (CUP), also known as the Young Turk Party, came to power in the Ottoman Empire. CUP ruled for ten years and created one of the first systems of totalitarian rule. In her ideology of Young Turks, an important place was occupied by the political concept of Ottomanism, which formed the ideological basis of CUP policy towards the non-Turkish peoples of the Empire. In this article, based on the analysis of the official documents of the Young Turks, the main features of its interpretation by this party are considered. As a result of the analysis of these documents, the author, for the first time in the historical literature, identifies the main stages in the evolution of Ottomanism in interpreting the Unity and Progress Party. He concludes that at the final stage, Ottomanism began to appear as Muslim Ottomanism. This was the result of the fact that, because of the policy of genocide, the Christian Armenian population, which constituted the majority of Christians in the Ottoman Empire, was destroyed physically.

Keywords: Ottoman Empire, Ottomanism, Young Turks, Committee of Union and Progress, Christian subjects, official documents.

The official documents of the Committee of Union And Progress (further: CUP) we used are divided into two groups. The first group is the CUP political Programs, which were adopted by the Young Turks' Congresses of 1908 and 1913 and were amended by the Congresses of 1911 and 1916, as well as the regulations adopted in 1909 and 1913 and partially amended in 1911 and 1916. We were studying these documents to reveal how the theoretical provisions of Ottomanism were implemented during the transformation of his political concept.

The next group of documents used in the article is the circulating letters of the CUP Central Committee to his provincial representations, which determine the domestic political fundamental issues and give the theoretical basing of its domestic policy. K.N. Duru, who had been a member of the Young Turks party, published them. These documents are unique, as in the period of Constantinople's occupation by the allies; the archive of the Central Committee was lost. The circulating letters that were not for publication are valuable for they allow deeper understand Young Turks' political ideology.

Ottomanism has been essential in the ideology of the Young Turks movement since the period of the movement's formation. During the years before the coup d'état of 1908, the leaders of Young Turks were trying to use it mainly as an ideological base for the alliance with the parties and organizations of the non-Turkish peoples to dethrone despotic Sultan Abdul-Hamid II and to establish constitutional monarchy in the country. For this purpose, the Young Turks media widely propagated the ideas of "friendship and equality of all Ottomans" and "All-Ottoman patriotism."

Young Turks tried to ensure that the declaration of the Constitution would solve the country's problems, including national ones.

Coming to power in the July of 1908, Young Turks faced the following significant task. That is, to elaborate the bases of their policy concerning not Turk peoples proceeding from the general provisions of Ottomanism. The first attempt to solve this task was the party's August draft Program (1908).

It became a basis for the text of a Program adopted by the CUP Congress in the October of the same year (7, 65-67). The Program reflected the fundamental provisions of Ottomanism doctrine. Adhering to the concept elaborated yet by the "New Ottomans" of the 60-70s of the 19th century, the leaders of the constitutional movement, Young Turks, proclaimed all the peoples of Empire Ottomans, irrespective of their nationality and religion (66). As a synonym, the Program also used the phrase "Ottoman subjects." (7, 67). Non-Turk peoples of the Ottoman Empire were called "elements." (7, 67). Thus, the non-Turkish peoples, who were derived even of a right to be called by a separate ethnonym, were included in the so-called "Ottoman nation" as his component by the Program's authors.

All the "Ottomans," including non-Muslims, was declared independent and equal to the Law and could become civil servants without any difference. The Program also contained a point on the involvement of non-Muslims in the army. By these provisions, the Program's authors aspired to create a mirage of the possibility of reaching "equality and freedom" within the frameworks of the so-called "Ottoman nation" for the non-Turk peoples.

The provisions for educating non-Turk peoples' children in the spirit of devotion to the "Ottoman Motherland" had an important place in Ottomanism. This was reflected in the decisions adopted by Congress. Thus, point 13 of the decisions published in the newspaper "Shura-i Ummet" confirmed that "the most im-

portant of the public initiatives was distribution and development of education." (7, 65). The study of relevant paragraphs allows for determining what was meant.

In the sphere of education, the most important goal of the policy was declared "education" of Ottoman non-Turkish peoples in the spirit of "unity and order."

The methods of reaching this goal are the determination of state control over all the schools in the Empire, including over non-Turks' schools, the establishment of the so-called mixed schools, wherein children of Muslims and non-Muslims would study together, as well as compulsory education in the Turkish language at state schools.

All these provisions were taken from the "Law on People's Education" adopted during the period of reforms of Tanzimat in 1869 due to efforts of a group of the Empire's officials - supporters of the concept of "merge" of all peoples of Ottoman Empire and creating the so called "Ottoman Nation". However, Young Turks made the following amendment: the Law of 1869 created elementary state schools for the children of Muslims in the settlements where the greatest parts of the population were Muslims. In the meantime, The Program of Young Turks contains no such provision; it only says that the Turkish language in elementary schools is a compulsory subject. As a result, at the initial stage of CUP activity as a ruling party, it became clear that their interpretation of Ottomanism was more regressive than that of the figures of the Tanzimat period.

One of the crucial provisions of Ottomanism was the idea of spreading the single language of the "Ottoman nation" among the peoples of the Empire. This goal was to be achieved by including the paragraphs on maintaining the Turkish language as a state language and keeping the official procedure, including judicial proceedings, in Turkish and education at Turkish schools in the Program. A point was included in the Program on the extension of provincial authorities' powers on the exact maintenance of Article 108 of the Constitution of 1876. Young Turks are known to support the so-called centralized Ottomanism. However, proceeding from tactical intentions, they compromised with the non-Turk parties and organizations and the Prince Sabaheddin's grouping, which demanded decentralization of administrative power. The Program's fifth paragraph became a result of this compromise (7, 66).

In the second Congress of CUP (1909), the party's Program underwent some changes, though the Congress decided to leave it mainly unchanged. In particular, under the influence of the criticism of non-Turk peoples' representatives, a point was included in the Program that at the elementary schools of the first degree, "the language of teaching must be the language of the local people." (7,82). This softening of position is explained by the fact that after the regressive rebel's dispersal in 1909, Young Turks made compromises with national minorities to maintain their authority.

The same Congress approved the party's Internal Regulations (7, 67-79) which does not touch upon the issues related to Ottomanism.

The study of the Program of Young Turks of 1908-09 shows that after coming to power, they elaborated a

Program of Ottomanization of the multi-nation population of the Ottoman Empire based on the concepts of Tanzimat leaders.

The methods to achieve that goal were as follows:

- Wide propaganda of devotion to "equality and friendship among all "Ottomans", as well as to the "Ottoman nation" and to the "Ottoman Motherland". According to the leaders of Young Turks the non-Turk peoples included in "Ottoman nation" as his "elements".

- Through the system of people's educational institutions under state control, "education of non-Turk peoples 'in the spirit of devotion to the Ottoman Motherland."

- The forced spreading of the Turkish language as the single language of the "Ottoman nation."

Factually, it was a Program of partly Turkization of non-Turk peoples.

It is not surprising that the implementation of that Program faced many difficulties caused by the opposition of Arabs, Armenians, Greeks, and other suppressed people against these plans. The leaders of the Young Turks were probably aware that the policy of "Ottomanization" was failing. On the second anniversary of the 1908 coup d'état, Young Turks' newspaper "Tanin" published the call of the leadership of CUP, admitting that the efforts to create "unity" between various peoples of Empire failed. One of the leaders of Young Turks, Talaat, also had to admit that fact in his speech to the participants of the discussion behind closed doors during the non-formal meeting the leading members of CUP (5, 100-102).

At the same time, Young Turks had not refused yet from the policy of Ottomanization developed in 1908. The above-mentioned Call said that the efforts towards the creation of unity would be continued.

The issue connected with the policy of Ottomanism was one of the major topics of the party's regular Congress in 1910. The Congress confirmed CUP devotion to Ottomanism. It was said that Young Turks aspired for the unity of the Empire's peoples and not for their assimilation (5, 99). That specification was probably made under the influence of ideas of Zia Gökalp who was responsible for the ideology. His point of view, which he had published yet in 1909 in "Peyman" magazine, won the Congress. According to it, "Ottoman does not mean Turk," hence Ottomanization of the non-Turkish peoples is senseless (8, 223). Zia enjoyed the patronage of Talaat. Later he created his interpretation of ideology of Turkism/Panturkism and became its leader.

In any case, as it will be show below, that provision was one of the fundamental ones in the concept of Ottomanism that was formulated in the circulating letter of the CUP Central Committee addressed to provincial party organizations on November 14-15, 1911. (Zia Gökalp is considered the author of that document).

The period after the Congress's was remarkable with the constantly increasing crisis in Young Turks circles. In conditions of growing dissatisfaction with the regime of CUP in the country and acuteness of the national issue, various groupings were forming in the

elite circles of Young Turks, who had disagreements, especially as regards the optimal methods to keep the non-Turkish Christian people as part of the Empire. Thus, in the spring of 1911, the members of the party's parliamentary faction "Unity and Progress" established a grouping of nonconformists called "Hisb-i Cedid" (New Party). The Program advanced by members of "Hisb-i Cedid" provided the necessity of waging the policy of unification again, but it mentioned no specific measures of unifying the "elements" of Ottoman nation (6, 153).

The grouping of Talaat that had gained a ruling position in the party sought new ways of Ottomanization more intensively. The ideologist of that grouping was above-mentioned Ziya Gökalp. The contours of Ottomanism's new interpretation could be observed more precisely already in 1911. In this connection, the circulating letter of the Central Committee of Young Turks dated November 14-15, 1911 was an interesting document (3, 48-52). This document gives a new description of Ottomanism. The author writes that after the restoration of the Constitution, various interpretations of Ottomanism were gradually revealed. To avoid chaos in this issue, he suggests two levels of Ottomanism: social and political. Social Ottomanism unites separate members of society, and the political one unites separate "elements", i.e., peoples. The supporters of the concepts "assimilation" and "accord" were confusing these two levels. The supporters of "assimilation" stated that Ottomanism united persons, while those of "accord" thought Ottomanism united separate peoples. Both cases were wrong, as they did not consider such phenomena as language, history, literature, and religion: these values deserve respect from the social point of view. However, from the political point of view, "the elements of the Ottoman nation" has no individual rights. Adopting such rights will mean contributing to liquidating "Ottoman unity." The only correct point of view was that of CUP, which stated that the elements of the Ottoman nation had a right to difference in the aspects of language, literature, and others from the viewpoint of "social Ottomanism." However, from the point of view of "political Ottomanism," they had no special rights. The first striking thing in the above concept's analysis is the refusal of the idea of full Ottomanization of the Empire's peoples, the idea in which Young Turks exerted such great efforts and emphasized as a primary goal in their first Program. The failure of the policy of "Ottomanization" was the most likely to have a critical impact on the development of that new interpretation of Ottomanism, which faced strong opposition from non-Turk peoples. The admission that full "Ottomanization" of non-Turk peoples was impossible became a crucial point for Young Turks' policy on the national issue. On the one hand, they continued propagating the idea of friendship and unity among all the Ottomans; on the other hand, they applied other ideological and political doctrines: Pan-Islamism and Pan-Turkism.

The new ideology and policy issues were discussed at the fourth Congress of Young Turks in 1911. Unfortunately, the decisions of that Congress have not

been fully published so far. In conformity with an opinion prevailing in literature, secret decisions of the Congress provided for a change from Ottomanism to Pan-Islamism and Pan-Turkism.

The Congress revised and considerably replenished the Statute of Young Turks party (7, 83-99). Some provisions in the spirit of Ottomanism were included in it. However, they differed somewhat from the relevant points of the party's Program adopted in 1908. Thus, Young Turks pledged to "prevent" the realization of the goals of those who aspired to stir up separatism and rebellions among all the Ottomans using national and religious differences and other methods. Thus, the "Ottomans' calls for unity" and the provisions on equality in the Statute of 1911 were replaced with threats addressed to the "separatists." It should be taken into account that the Statute was not designed for publication. At the same time, in the applications to the people in various "Calls", which Young Turks were resorting to very often, especially in connection with the Tripolitanian and Balkan wars, the ideas of "Ottoman patriotism" were propagandized. The calls of CUP in connection with the Tripolitanian war were very characteristic (1).

The above tendencies were strengthening in 1911-13. In 1913, the leadership of Young Turks formulated the bases of the new policy in the national issue (2, 314). They were gradually displayed in the party's documents.

The analysis of the texts of the Program (7, 106-110) and Statute (7, 110-118) of Young Turks adopted by the Congress of 1913 testifies to their gradual refusal of Ottomanism. One can find an Ottoman provision only in the 41st paragraph of the party's Program, which was dedicated to education issues: the goal of spreading education in the country was to achieve unity of the "Ottoman nation" (7, 109-110).

One can arrive at the same conclusion by also studying the circulating letter of the party "Unity and Progress," which is entitled "About the ways of managing the official initiatives by the Organization" ("Unity and Progress" – R.S.) (3, 42-47). It can be dated approximately 1913. This document expresses concern that non-Muslim peoples managed to better use the Constitutional rights and freedoms by transforming their "bands" into political parties in a country wherein the state religion is Islam; there originated danger that non-Muslim peoples would come to power. That is why CUP faced several tasks: to hold parliamentary elections without infringing the state's interests, i.e., not allowing non-Muslim parties to gain the majority in the parliament, and to gather the majority of the elected deputies around their Program. Thus, this document, factually, declares the refusal of the task to achieve "unity of all the Ottomans." A new task was set to the party: to protect the "interests" of the Empire's Muslims.

The other two circulating letters dated approximately 1914 already theoretically ground the necessity of a policy aiming protection of the interests of Muslims and Turks in prejudice of non-Muslim peoples' interests (3, 53-62, 67-76). One of these letters criticized the policy of "assimilation" concerning non-Muslims in

the period of Tanzimat. The author says that it reduced the spheres of Islam's influence in the country. Restoration of Islam's role is possible through a policy of "Muslim Ottomanism," which provides for Muslims to remain the ruling "element". At the same time, it is necessary to aspire to unite Muslims.

These provisions were reflected in the amendments to the party's Program made by the Congress of 1916, after the decision on "Final Solution" of the Armenian Question and its implementation in the form of policy of genocide of Armenian people (7, 118-120). Thus, for example, paragraph 1 mentioned the role that Sheik-al-Islam's office was to play in the issue of reverse reform's implementation. Provisions in the spirit of Islamism were also included in the remaining paragraphs of the CUP Program. It was not accidental that Zia Gökalp was assessing the results of the Congress in the magazine "Islam," noting the increase in the influence of Islam on the policy of the Young Turks party (4, 60).

Thus, studying the party documents allows to identify the periods of Ottomanism's evolution during rule of CUP. From 1908-1909 Ottomanism was considered an ideological and political doctrine, which implementation would allow refusals of the non-Muslim peoples from their national-liberation movement on the one hand and would create conditions for their gradual Turkization on the other hand. However, already in 1910, a crisis of the so-called "traditional" interpretation of Ottomanism inherited from the Tanzimat's figures and the Constitutional movement of "New Ottomans" could be observed. As a result, in 1911 the repressive aspect strengthened in it. At the same time, the search for new ideological and political systems started in conditions of more and more precisely revealed inefficiency of the doctrine. The last version of Ottomanism was the so-called "Muslim Ottomanism," which

aimed at achieving the "unity" of the Empire's Muslims. Factually, Ottomanism changed the diversity of Pan-Islamism used in Young Turks' domestic policy. As a result of his analysis, the author concludes that at the final stage, Ottomanism began to appear in the form of Muslim Ottomanism. This was the result of the fact that, because of the policy of genocide, the Christian Armenian population, which constituted the majority of Christians, Ottoman Empire was destroyed physically.

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